

MECHANISM OF FISSION OF ETHERS. PART I. FISSION OF AROMATIC ETHERS IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

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Fission of aromatic ethers by HCl or HBr in various non-aqueous solvents has been studied and a mechanism of the reaction suggested.

The kinetics of the reaction of halogen acids and the ethers has been studied in acetic and formic acid solution by various workers (Ghaswalla and Donnan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1341; Birosel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 85, 1403). The reaction is represented by the following equation

where R is an alkyl radical and X is Cl, Br or I.

This reaction has been termed as hydrolysis of ethers by most of the workers, however, as the equation shows, water does not take part in the reaction at all. The more appropriate term appears to be fission or cleavage of an ether by a halogen acid. Instead of hydrolysis, the term fission, therefore, has been used in the present work to represent the above reaction.

Ghaswalla and Donnan (*loc. cit.*) have studied the mechanism of fission of aromatic ethers by hydrogen bromide using 95% acetic acid as solvent. These authors have proposed the following mechanism :—

The reversible equation shown in (ii) is instantaneous and the oxonium complex is completely ionised. It will be observed therefore, that the reaction mechanism assumes the formation of the oxonium salt. Recently Meerwin, Hinz, Hofmann, Kroning and Pfeil (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1937, ii, 147, 257) have isolated salt like oxonium compounds with ethers. In these compounds the first three valencies of oxygen are co-valent and the fourth valency is electrovalent.

The object of the present work is to throw more light on the mechanism of fission of aromatic ethers by HCl or HBr. In the present work, therefore, the fission of aromatic ethers in various non-aqueous solvents has been studied and a mechanism has been proposed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Anisole was purchased from Kahlbaum. The remaining ethers, *p*-chloroanisole, *p*-nitroanisole, *o*-nitroanisole and *p*-methylanisole were prepared by methylating the corresponding phenols according to standard methods. *p*-Bromoanisole was prepared according to the method of Birosel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1944). The ethers were purified by fractional distillation or crystallisation. All the purified samples of ethers had physical constants which agreed very well with the standard values.

The solvents, benzene, *n*-hexane, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform were carefully dried and purified by the usual methods.

Hydrogen chloride was prepared by the action concentrated sulphuric acid on pure ammonium chloride. Hydrogen bromide was prepared by gently warming pure potassium bromide with a syrupy mixture of phosphoric acid and phosphorus pentoxide according to the method of Fairbrother (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 862).

Procedure.—In these experiments the halogen acid was passed in the solution of the ether in the solvent in a tube till the necessary concentration was obtained and the tube was sealed

and was heated at 70° in a thermostat. After a certain time the tube was taken out, chilled in ice and opened; the contents were transferred to a flask containing distilled water. The halogen acid was titrated against standard sodium hydroxide. The unchanged ether was extracted with ether and washed with a slight excess of sodium hydroxide. The alkaline extract was used for the estimation of phenol as described by Ghaswala and Donnan (*loc. cit.*). In some of the experiments the effect of the addition of small quantities of acetic acid, pyridine, dimethylaniline and aniline was studied. In these experiments and also in the case of anisidine the unchanged ether was weighed out and the extent of fission calculated. Experiments were carried out a stage further in the case of anisidine. It was thought that the following reaction

might take place in preference to the usual reaction. The reaction mixture of hydrogen bromide and anisidine in carbon tetrachloride was acidified and the carbon tetrachloride was removed and washed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The aqueous solution and the washings were made alkaline and extracted with ether and the ether removed; after drying the residue was weighed. It was found that this residue contained bromine. This was attributed to the presence of *p*-bromoaniline formed according to the equation (iv). Analysis showed, however, that *p*-bromoaniline was present to the extent of 1% only, the rest being anisidine. The experiment shows that the reaction (iv) takes place only to a small extent.

In these experiments it was difficult to maintain exactly the same concentration of the halogen acid in all the experiments, and therefore assuming a proportionality between the concentration of the halogen acid and the percentage fission, all the results for percentage fission have been calculated for a particular concentration of the halogen acid as indicated in the tables. Attempt was made, however, to maintain the concentration of the halogen acid as near as possible to the concentration mentioned in the table. The error in the estimation of phenols generated is about 0.5%. Results of these experiments and a discussion thereon are given below.

R E S U L T S

The following tables give the results of the fission of ethers with hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide in carbon tetrachloride and hexane solutions.

TABLE I

Solvent = CCl ₄ . Reagent = HCl (0.1 M).			
Ether (0.1 M)	Temp.	Time.	% Fission.
Anisole	70°	10 hours	0.90
Anisole	70°	50	0.80
Anisole	70°	40	0.70
Anisole (0.5 M)	25-30°	5 months	0.90
<i>p</i> -Methylanisole	70°	10 hours	0.50
<i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	70°	10	0.35
<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	70°	10	0.45
<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	70°	10	0.35

TABLE II

Solvent = CCl ₄ . Reagent = HBr (0.5 M).			
Ether (0.1 M)	Temp.	Time.	% Fission.
Anisole	70°	9 hours	0.96
<i>p</i> -Chloroanisole	..	..	0.55
<i>p</i> -Methylanisole	..	..	1.20
<i>p</i> -Bromoanisole	..	..	0.75
<i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	..	..	0.43
<i>o</i> -Nitroanisole	..	..	0.77

TABLE III
Solvent = *n*-Hexane.

Reagent.	Ether.	Temp.	Time.	% Fission.
HCl (0.5 M)	Anisole	25-30°	3½ months	1.00
HBr (0.5 M)	Anisole	70°	10 hours	0.40

It will be observed from the above tables that the fission of anisole by hydrogen chloride was less than 1% even after 50 hours at 70° in sealed tubes. The fission did not proceed further even on keeping the reaction mixture for five months at room temperature (25-30°) (Table I). The observed fission (1%) may be due to experimental errors in the estimations of free phenol generated, since the fission is small (about 0.5%) in the case of all the others studied in carbon tetrachloride and *n*-hexane solutions.

Experiments (Table II) were tried with hydrogen bromide but fission was again under 1%. It may, therefore, be concluded that the fission of ethers does not take place appreciably in *n*-hexane and carbon tetrachloride solutions in the presence of hydrogen chloride or bromide.

The halogen acids are not ionised in carbon tetrachloride or *n*-hexane, and hence the results given in the above table show that unionised HCl or HBr is unable to bring about the fission of ethers in these solvents.

These important results showed that the mechanism of the reaction might be similar to acid base catalysed reactions. Working from analogy (*e.g.*, mutarotation of glucose by Lowry) the effect of the presence of bases in these solvents was studied.

In the first instance the effect of introduction of pyridine in the reaction mixture was tried and the results were according to expectations (Table IV). The increase in reaction took place appreciably but to a small extent in anisole with hydrogen chloride, therefore; further experiments were carried out with hydrogen bromide instead of hydrogen chloride. The following table summarises the results.

TABLE IV

Base = 5% Pyridine. Reagent = *M*-HBr. Temp. = 70°. Time = 10 hr. Solvent = CCl₄.

Ether ...	Anisole	<i>p</i> -Chloro-	<i>p</i> -Bromo-	<i>p</i> -Methyl-	<i>o</i> -Nitro-	<i>p</i> -Nitro-
% Fission...	37.12 (*2.68) (28.73**)	20.08	6.52	4.42	1.54	4.45
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* Figure denotes fission with 1M-HCl for 11 hours.

** The figure denotes fission with 1M-HBr for 10 hours in *n*-hexane.

Further in order to make the experiments more comprehensive the effect of other bases like dimethylaniline and aniline was also studied and the following table shows the results.

TABLE V

Solvent = CCl₄. Reagent = 1.0M-HBr. Temp. = 70°.

Ether (0.5 M).	Base (5%).	Time.	% Fission.
Anisole	Dimethylaniline	10 hours	78.39
Anisole	Aniline	"	64.79
Anisidine	—	9 hours	79.37

The effect of pyridine on the extent of fission is very striking. Thus in the case of anisole the fission by 0.5M-hydrogen bromide was about 1% in carbon tetrachloride (Table II) while in the presence of pyridine the fission was nearly 37.1% with 1.0 M-hydrogen bromide (Table IV). In *n*-hexane likewise the fission increased from 0.4 to 28.7% under the same conditions (Table IV). The results with dimethylaniline and aniline are similar (Table V). These experiments indicate that the presence of a base is an important factor in the reaction.

Ghaswalla and Donnan (*loc. cit.*) showed that the reaction took place easily in 95% acetic acid as solvent. In this case the function of the base in the reaction may be attributed to acetic acid.

In order to see the effect of acetic acid in small quantities on the extent of fission of the ethers and also to study the extent of fission in glacial acetic acid, several experiments were carried out and the results are given in the following tables.

TABLE VI

Solvent = CCl₄. Reagent = 0.5 M-HBr. Temp. = 70°. Time = 6 hours.
Conc. of acetic acid = 5%.

Ether (0.5M)	Anisole	<i>p</i> -Chloro-	<i>p</i> -Bromo-	<i>p</i> -Methyl-	<i>o</i> -Nitro-	<i>p</i> -Nitro-
%Fission	9.26	3.85	3.28	6.62	3.77	2.04

TABLE VII

Anisole (0.5M).

Solvent = acetic acid (glacial).

Reagent.	Temp.	Time.	%Fission.
HCl (0.37N)	25-30°	3½ months	12.24
HCl (0.23N)	70°	42 hours	15.15
HBr (1.04N)	70°	10 hours	96.85

Solvent = 95% acetic acid.

HCl (0.24N)	25-30°	½ months	18.64
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From the above tables it will be observed that due to the presence of acetic acid the extent of fission increases from 1 to 9.2% in the case of anisole in carbon tetrachloride (*cf.* Tables II & VI). Similarly it will be seen that the reaction takes place to an appreciable extent in the case of glacial acetic acid and in 95% acetic acid. It has already been indicated that the presence of a base is an important factor in the fission of the ether. In this case also the accelerating effect due to the presence of acetic acid can be attributed to the acetic acid functioning as a base. On the Lowry and Bronsted theory of acids and bases, the anion is regarded as a base (proton acceptor) but in carbon tetrachloride or in hexane solution, acetic acid will not ionise at all. Hence the only way in which acetic acid can act as the base is by combining with the proton belonging to the halogen acid (solvation)

This type of solvation is supported by the very high solubility of hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide in acetic acid.

A few experiments have been carried out in non-hydroxylic solvents having different dielectric constants such as nitrobenzene, chloroform, etc. The following tables give the results.

TABLE VIII
Fission of ethers in different solvents
Temp. = 70°.

Solvent.	D.C.	Percentage fission of			D.C.	% Fission of anisole.
		anisole.	<i>p</i> -methylanisole.	nitroanisole.		
Nitrobenzene	36.45	65.7	42.0	3.5	36.45	99.79
Chloroform	5.14	29.9	38.8	2.25	5.14	54.67
Chlorobenzene	5.36	3.65	3.89	1.8	5.36	31.12
Acetic acid	9.0	71.66	50.47	—	9.0	96.45

It will be observed from the above table that the extent of fission is greater in the solvent with higher dielectric constant (D.C.) and the reaction proceeds still further with the addition of a catalyst like pyridine.

The above experimental observations bring out the following points :—

(i) Hydrogen chloride or bromide are co-valent compounds in non-polar solvents and under these conditions the reaction between the acid and the aromatic ethers does not take place.

(ii) The reaction can take place in non-polar solvents if a base like pyridine, dimethylaniline or aniline is present. The base forms a salt with the halogen acid and the co-valent link between the halogen and the hydrogen atom changes into an electrovalent link, the hydrogen atom joining itself to the base. A hydroxylic solvent like acetic acid can also function as a base by the solvation of the proton of the halogen acid.

(iii) Hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide react very easily with ethers in a polar solvent like acetic acid, formic acid, propionic acid, nitrobenzene, chloroform, etc. (*cf.* Ghaswalla and Donnan *loc. cit.* Biresel *loc. cit.* Bapat and Kolhatkar, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1938, III, 8, 157).

(iv) The halogen acids can react with the aromatic ethers only when the bond between the hydrogen and the halogen changes from co-valent to electrovalent type.

This can be achieved by the presence of (a) a proton acceptor like pyridine, aniline, dimethylaniline or (b) hydroxylic solvents like acetic acid, or, (c) a solvent with a high dielectric constant like nitrobenzene.

The following mechanism can therefore be proposed for the fission of ethers by halogen acids :—

(a) Fission of ethers in presence of a base (pyridine = Py).

(b) Fission of ethers in the presence of a hydroxylic solvent like acetic acid.

Reaction (1) and (2) are reversible and rapid. While reactions (3) and (4) are slow and determine the rate of the reaction. Mechanism proposed in (b) requires some remarks. Acetic acid acts as a base (proton acceptor) according to the following equation:—

This equilibrium cannot go very far to the right. The halogen acid will therefore be weak, in the sense that the extent of ionisation and conductance will be smaller than those for the corresponding acid in water; even acids like perchloric acid which are highly ionised in water appear to be dissociated to a small extent in acetic acid. It is a very striking fact, however, that the hydrogen ion activity in such solutions is exceptionally high, much higher than in aqueous solutions so that they have been termed *superacids* (Hall and Conant, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 3047, 3052).

This activity is attributed to the fact that the $(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}_2)^+$ ion has a marked tendency to loose a proton. The same observation applies to formic acid as well. The high proton activity well enable the formation of the oxonium salt and hence the great ease with which the others are split up in acetic, formic or propionic acids as medium is accounted for.

The mechanism is not different from the one proposed by Ghaswalla and Donnan (*loc. cit.*) and is not in conflict with the kinetic measurements carried out by them. These authors, however, did not consider the rôle of the solvent functioning as a base in the mechanism of the reaction.

Our experiments on the fission of anisole in nitrobenzene and other solvents deserve some remarks. It is well known that hydrogen chloride or bromide is not highly ionised in these solvents. The low conductivity must be due to the formation of ion pairs. Ionisation of the halogen acid in solvents like nitrobenzene and chloroform enables oxonium salt formation and therefore fission can occur. In hexane and carbon tetrachloride the halogen acids are not at all ionised. In nitrobenzene the fission is greater than in chloroform because of its higher dielectric constant. Chlorobenzene and chloroform have the same dielectric constants but the fission takes place to a much greater extent in chloroform than in chlorobenzene. It appears, therefore, that apart from the dielectric constant the solvent can have its own specific effect.

In the proposed mechanism it will be observed that the rate determining factor is the reaction between the halogen anion and the alkyl group (CH_3). The introduction of a negative group in the phenoxy radical will make the bond between the alkyl and the phenoxy radical stronger as the alkyl group is electro-positive. The rate of the reaction between the alkyl group and the halogen ion will be diminished. The observed order of fission $\text{H} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{NO}_2$ due to the influence of groups introduced in the phenoxy radical (Ghaswalla and Donnan, *loc. cit.*) bears out this point.

The results of fission of *p*-methylanisole show some peculiar results. Ghaswalla and Donnan (*loc. cit.*) found that the rate of fission was very great with *p*-methylanisole ($k = 102 \times 10^{-4}$) as compared with anisole ($k = 71.40 \times 10^{-4}$). Our results in the case of HBr and pyridine in carbon tetrachloride solution (Table IV), HBr and acetic acid in carbon tetrachloride solution (Table VI) and HBr in nitrobenzene (Table VIII) show greater fission of anisole than that of *p*-methylanisole, while in chloroform (Table VIII) the order is reversed.

Further work is in progress.